

ANNUAL REPORT 2023

Image life, *discover the future*

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We are the European landmark Research Infrastructure for biological and biomedical imaging as recognized by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI). Euro-BioImaging is the gateway to 237 world-class imaging facilities across Europe.

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ABOUT US

FOREWORD

John Eriksson
Director general

Antje Keppler
Bio-Hub Section Director

Linda Chaabane
Med-Hub Section Director

Annual reports provide a valuable opportunity to pause, reflect on the past year's joint achievements, and 2023 was truly extraordinary for Euro-Biolmaging! Our success was possible thanks to the strong support and collaboration of our members, stakeholders, dedicated team, and our inspiring, ever-expanding community.

A significant highlight of 2023 was the strategic addition of two new members to our consortium. In December, we welcomed Belgium and Spain, further demonstrating and reinforcing European interest in joining our landmark research infrastructure. After just four years, Euro-Biolmaging proudly counts 19 members. Adding new members is an intense and multifaceted process, but highly rewarding, resulting from high-level discussions, alignment of interests, and the development of trust-based relationships. We are delighted to witness the transformation of all the initial enthusiasm we have experienced into long-term strategic engagement to advance science and innovation.

In 2023, Euro-Biolmaging built significant momentum, carefully laying the solid groundwork for our next development phase. Having spent four years building and strengthening our foundations, we are now well prepared and positioned to overcome future obstacles. One of the key reasons for this readiness is the finalisation of our next five-year financial plan, a testimony to the commitment of our membership and stakeholders to ensure the

economic stability of our research infrastructure. We are truly grateful for the commitment that we observed, as this plan sets the stage for our long-term operational capacity, a critical requirement for engagement and trust from stakeholders, team members, and our community. We also developed and finalised our Strategic Plan for 2024-2028, a significant milestone that captures our vision for the future of imaging in Europe. Our Strategic Plan, in particular, outlines a strategic path for advancing imaging in Europe. Its six goals are in perfect harmony with EVOLVE, an INFRA-DEV project funded by the European Commission, aimed at enhancing the ERIC implementation and operation. EVOLVE will significantly boost and amplify the role of Euro-Biolmaging in the European Research Area, enhancing our scientific capacity, our visibility, stakeholder engagement, operational excellence, and impact as a key driver of research and innovation.

Throughout 2023, we accomplished numerous milestones, detailed in the following pages of the Annual Report. As we move forward, we carry the momentum and determination from 2023, ready to reach new heights in 2024 in close partnership with our members, stakeholders, and the entire imaging and scientific community.

We very much look forward to the continued and shared journey to shape the future of imaging and to advance the European research and innovation landscape.

INFRASTRUCTURE AT A GLANCE

Euro-Biolmaging ERIC is the European Research Infrastructure Consortium for biological and biomedical imaging, awarded the landmark status by ESFRI and thus recognized as the implemented reference infrastructure in the imaging field. Euro-Biolmaging was established as an ERIC in the end of 2019.

The distributed Euro-Biolmaging infrastructure builds on a set of already existing national and international facilities of excellence in imaging technologies, the Euro-Biolmaging Nodes, which provide physical or remote access to imaging technologies, deliver training, and support the users at all stages of their research projects with their experienced staff.

Every researcher, both from academia and industry, can apply for Euro-Biolmaging services whenever they have a project requiring imaging technologies and expertise but do not have the equipment or the skills to perform experiments at their home institute.

The Nodes are jointly coordinated by the Euro-Biolmaging Hub, which provides general supporting services including the management of user access, policy and lobbying, community and skill building activities, and services for image data.

19

MEMBERS
(COUNTRIES & EMBL)

As of May 2024

41

NODES

As of May 2024

237

IMAGING
FACILITIES

As of May 2024

Euro-BioImaging members and facilities as of May 2024

● Cities where Euro-BioImaging facilities are located

● Members

● Hub sites hosts
Statutory Seat (Finland)
Bio-Hub (EMBL)
Med-Hub (Italy)

120+

TECHNOLOGIES &
IMAGE DATA SERVICES

As of May 2024

616

USER
PROJECTS

As of May 2024

19

EU-FUNDED
PROJECTS

As of May 2024

HIGHLIGHTS OF 2023

OUR TEAM

Statutory Seat
Turku, Finland

Bio-Hub
EMBL, Germany

Med-Hub
Torino, Italy

JOHN ERIKSSON
Director General

ANTJE KEPPLER
Section Director
Bio-Hub

LINDA CHAABANE
Section Director
Med-Hub

AMARANTA AMADOR
Head of Legal
Services and
International
Relations

DANIELA AVILES HUERTA
Scientific Project
Manager

JOHANNA BISCHOF
Head of Bio-Hub
Operations

ERIKA CERUTTI
Project Manager

MARIANNA CHILDRESS POLI
External
Communications
Officer

GIUSEPPE DIGILIO
Operations
Advisor

DOROTHEA DÖRR
Scientific
Project
Manager

AYOUB EL GHADRAOUI
EU Project
Manager

SOLVEIG ERIKSSON
Multimedia
Producer

JIRI FUNDA
Project
Manager

CAMILO GUZMÁN
Scientific Officer
Quality Manager
of Biological
Imaging

DALE LAWSON
Senior Scientific
Project Manager

ANTING LI
Personal
Assistant to the
Management

DARIO LONGO
Scientific Project
Manager

RAKESH MAHATO
Software
Developer

AASTHA MATHUR
Head of
Image Data
Services

MARIA MIRZA
Scientific Project
Manager

FERIEL RAMDHANE
Image Data
Scientist

MARCELA RIVERA
Junior Scientific
Officer

ZORICA RUOHONEN
Finance and
Administration
Manager

ARINA RYBINA
Scientific Project
Manager

JAANUS SAARNAK
Software
Developer

BEATRIZ SERRANO-SOLANO
Scientific Project
Manager

OUR MISSION

**LAURENT
CHMIEL**
Communications
Officer

**SUDEEP
DAS**
Project Manager

**RAFAEL
DIAZ**
Junior Scientific
Officer

**ANNE-CHARLOTTE
JOUBERT**
EU Project
Manager

**PASI
KANKAANPÄÄ**
Senior Scientific
Manager

**ISABEL
KEMMER**
FAIR Image Data
Steward

**BUĞRA
ÖZDEMİR**
Image Data
Specialist

**CLAUDIA
PFANDER**
Industry Board
Coordinator &
External Relations
Manager

**ILARI
PULLI**
Head of
Operations

**SUSANNE
VAINIO**
Scientific Officer
Quality Manager
of Medical
Imaging

**ALESSANDRA
VIALE**
Head of Med-Hub
Operations

**AMAN
YADAV**
Software
Developer

We empower researchers with open access to innovative biological and biomedical imaging technologies, expertise, data services, and training.

We enable cutting-edge research and contribute to addressing pressing societal challenges. As an ERIC and an ESFRI Landmark Research Infrastructure, Euro-Biolmaging contributes to the overall competitiveness of the European Research Area and participates in global imaging initiatives.

GOVERNANCE

Euro-BioImaging is managed by its Hub and governed by the Euro-BioImaging Board. Our governance also includes a Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), to oversee the scientific, ethical, technical and quality management of the Euro-BioImaging ERIC activities. The Panel of Nodes, representing the individual Nodes, advises the Euro-BioImaging Directorate on operational matters concerning the Nodes and service provision. In addition, the Industry Board Advisory Panel provides input for the Directorate on industry-relevant aspects. The governing bodies meet regularly and actively contribute to the operations and development of our infrastructure.

In 2023, the Scientific Advisory Board contributed to the evaluation of new technologies and helped us develop and implement a new procedure for the Call for Nodes and Node Upgrades.

We also collaborated closely with the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board (EBIB) Advisory Panel and our Industry Board. April 2023 saw the first in person edition of the Euro-BioImaging All-Hands Nodes meeting, followed by an Industry Board-organised workshop on “BioImaging and the European Open Science Cloud.”

8th Board meeting, Turku, Finland

On May 23-24, 2023, Euro-BioImaging Board members met in Turku, Finland, to discuss the new Strategic and Finance Plan for Euro-BioImaging 2024-2028. At this meeting, the Board also elected Professor Maddy Parsons as the new Board Chair. She is Professor of Cell Biology, Director of the Microscopy Innovation Centre (which is part of our UK Node) and Vice Dean for Impact and Innovation at King's College London. She joins Jan Buriánek, the Board's Co-Chair, in leading the Euro-BioImaging Board. This meeting also gave us the opportunity to recognise the extraordinary service and support of Professor Benjamin Geiger, Board Chair since 2015. His remarkable commitment has contributed to the development of the infrastructure and ensured the seamless transition from interim phase to operations, a critical phase in the Euro-BioImaging growth and development.

All-Hands Nodes Meeting, EMBL

The Panel of Nodes (PoN) comprises an official representative from each of the 41 Euro-BioImaging Nodes. In 2023, Marc van Zandvoort and Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez, co-chairs, of the PoN held monthly meetings with the Euro-BioImaging Directorate to advise on matters concerning the Nodes. In addition, they contributed to organising and chairing of the All-Hands Nodes Meeting, from April 17-20, 2023, at EMBL Heidelberg, with Node staff and industry partners, pictured above.

**ACHIEVEMENTS
IN 2023**

OVERVIEW

We continued to surpass the goals set in our first strategic plan while setting the stage for our second strategic plan. Below we highlight our operational achievements in 2023 and set the stage for the future.

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS 2023

In our fourth year of operations, expansion continued to be our key word. The number of user projects increased rapidly, in part thanks to funding from the ISIDORE project (see IMPACT section for some examples).

Furthermore, we added two new member states, Spain and Belgium, to bring us to a membership of 19 countries and EMBL in December 2023. In parallel, we continued to influence the future of imaging through technological developments at our Nodes, participating in three Horizon Europe funded INFRA-TECH projects which launched in 2023, and by reaching over 120 imaging technologies in our portfolio.

Image data analysis services continued to thrive at our Nodes and we were awarded European funding for the founding GIDE project, to drive the development of a global image data ecosystem.

Strategic achievements in 2023 include the finalisation and approval by our Board of our next strategic plan for 2024-2028 and the aligned Financial Plan. This commitment by our member states, along with our successful EU funding application for the EVOLVE project, means that our infrastructure has the funding it needs to strengthen our foundations and shape the future of imaging over the next five years.

Thanks to the great support and engagement from our Board members, it is clear that Euro-Biolmaging is prepared for the challenges of a dynamic world, and we are confident that the strengths and assets built in our first operational phase will allow us to contribute significantly to the European Research Area and support the European and global imaging community, as we embark on our next phase of development.

NEW MEMBER STATES

On December 13, 2023, Euro-BioImaging welcomed Spain and Belgium as its newest member countries, significantly expanding imaging horizons in Europe. With these new members, six new Nodes representing seventeen imaging facilities joined Euro-BioImaging in January 2024.

Spain's membership to Euro-BioImaging ERIC has been achieved during the Spanish presidency of the European Union. "It has been a long process," says Inmaculada Figueroa on behalf of the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, Kingdom of Spain. "All the Spanish partners congratulate us for this and are eager to start the year engaged actively in Euro-BioImaging ERIC activities."

Belgium's membership in Euro-BioImaging ERIC has received strong support from the Flemish Department of Economy, Science and Innovation and the Belgian Science Policy Office, responsible for Belgium's participation in the ESFRI Roadmap.

Michele Oleo, Department of Economy, Science and Innovation Flanders, has been actively involved in Euro-BioImaging since

the preparatory phase. She commented that "Euro-BioImaging ERIC is undoubtedly one of the strongholds in the European Research Infrastructure landscape. I am delighted that our Node will be part of this scientific community."

Laurent Ghys, of the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO), who has also been following the membership process for many years, explained, "It was a long and difficult process, but we are very happy to finally achieve full member status."

Belgium has been active in Euro-BioImaging as an observer for a very long time, and full membership now gives access to Euro-BioImaging to the whole Belgian science community - opening the way to new collaborations and possible future Nodes.

“

The addition of Spain and Belgium to Euro-BioImaging, bringing our total membership to 19, was a remarkable milestone to conclude the year. Their strong commitment and expertise in bioimaging align with our goals and also promise to enrich our community with invaluable insights and contributions to facilitate excellent science and innovation.

John Eriksson
Euro-BioImaging Director General

NEW PROJECTS

To supplement our core funding and reach our ambitious objectives, Euro-BioImaging sought and was awarded two important Horizon Europe-funded projects in 2023 (HE-INFRA-2023-DEV-01).

The EVOLVE project (Grant Agreement #101130986) is a substantial advance in improving Euro-BioImaging's operability, capacity, and impact. EVOLVE will profoundly enhance Euro-BioImaging as a Research Infrastructure, both internally and externally. Spanning over three and a half years, the EVOLVE project perfectly aligns with Euro-BioImaging's Strategic Plan for 2024-2028. It will significantly strengthen our operation, administration, capacities for strategic partnering and capacity to facilitate innovation and excellent science. Furthermore, it will foster the family of Euro-BioImaging Nodes and Hub at the personal, institutional, national and European level.

eurobioimaging.eu/projects/evolve

◀ Scan to learn more about the **EVOLVE** project.

The acceptance of the foundingGIDE project (Grant Agreement #101130216) proposal by the European Commission is a significant milestone that validates the strategic importance of image data as a resource in the European and global scientific stages. This project will lay the foundation for a Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE) that connects different biological and biomedical image data resources across the globe to allow metadata and data sharing. GIDE will bring European research infrastructure and image data resource owners together with their counterparts from Australia (Universities of Queensland and Sydney) and Japan (RIKEN institute) to develop the basis of image data sharing, as well as engaging the global imaging community in the process.

founding-gide.eurobioimaging.eu

◀ Scan to learn more about the **foundingGIDE** project.

IMPACT

USER ACCESS

Euro-Biolmaging creates impact by offering open access to biological and biomedical imaging technologies, expertise, data analysis services, and training. Every researcher, both from academia and industry, can apply for Euro-Biolmaging services whenever they have a project requiring imaging technologies and expertise but do not have the equipment or skills to perform the experiments at their home institute. Here is how it works:

Initial consult

Potential users visit the Euro-Biolmaging web portal to select a technology and a Node, or contact Euro-Biolmaging directly to discuss their project and receive advice on technology and Node selection.

Access request

After the technology and Node are selected, the user fills in the request form via the Euro-Biolmaging web portal: eurobioimaging-access.eu

Scientific advice

Applications receive scientific advice from external experts to support project development. In certain cases, no scientific check is necessary and the proposal can be fast-tracked to the technical check.

Technical advice

The selected Node confirms the technical feasibility of the planned work. Once the access request is granted, the Node contacts the users regarding practicalities.

Service provision

A successful Euro-Biolmaging access request unlocks the power of imaging technologies and provides the expertise that users need to apply state-of-the-art imaging equipment to their project and analyze their results.

ABOUT OUR USERS

Euro-Biolmaging is open to researchers from all backgrounds and career stages, and any country in the world. The diversity of Euro-Biolmaging’s growing user base is highlighted in this two-page spread. To cover our first operational period, we feature data from 2020-2023, collected in the Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal (EWP).

Applications for user access

ALL APPLICATIONS

APPLICATIONS FROM INDUSTRY

This Key Performance Indicator quantifies the total number of applications for Euro-Biolmaging services that have been received in our web access portal during a given period of time, as well as all that have been accepted for access provision, respectively. The date of submission and date of approval for each application are taken into account for this KPI, resulting in some proposals being counted as received in one year and approved in the follow year. It provides clear information on the demand for our services.

We measure the number of applications received each year from industry users. Industry users self-identify as such during the application process and include both users from SMEs as well as large companies. It is our goal to see this type of applications increase further in the coming years.

(* In 2021, the Pilot User Access Fund led to an increase in the number of submitted applications.
 (**) Some of the submitted applications from the Pilot User Access Fund became accepted projects in 2022, explaining why there are more accepted applications than submitted applications in 2022.

User country of origin

Euro-Biolmaging users come from many countries with the highest concentration of users coming from Europe. Here we show the location of affiliation of all researchers who applied for Euro-Biolmaging services.

Variety of disciplines served

ISIDORe USER STORIES

Euro-Biolmaging participates in three EU-funded INFRA-SERV projects that bring together a number of Research Infrastructures to provide services free of charge to researchers working on specific research topics. ISIDORe (GA #101046133) provides funding for research on Infectious Diseases and pandemic preparedness, canSERV (GA #101058620) provides support for cancer research, and AgroServ (GA #101058020) aims at research in agroecology. As a project launched in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, ISIDORe has already supported a large range of research projects, including at Euro-Biolmaging Nodes, some of which we highlight here:

Understanding enterovirus replication in ultrastructural detail using cryo-Electron Tomography

Enteroviruses cause a range of diverse diseases in humans, including polio. Researchers from the Carlson Lab at University of Umeå in Sweden are studying how the virus forms inside human cells and how virus particles escape from infected cells. To identify the proteins involved in virus particle release, researchers Marie Sorin and Bina Kumari Singh, visited the Imaging Centre at EMBL, part of the EMBL Node, and used cryo-ET and FIB-milling.

From left to right: Marie Sorin, Zhengyi Yang, and Bina Kumari Singh examine their data in front of the cryo-ET machine at the EMBL Imaging Centre.
Photo: EMBL / PhotoLab, Massimo Del Prete

Structure of malaria pathogen identified using volumeEM

Pablo Suárez Cortés is a Postdoctoral researcher at the Max Planck Institute for Infection Biology, Berlin (Germany), working on how *Plasmodium falciparum*, the pathogen behind malaria, undergoes intricate transformations during its infection of *Anopheles* mosquitoes. In particular, Pablo aims to study secretory organelles of *Plasmodium* in its different transmission stages, but these are difficult to access and identify in vivo.

Pablo worked with the experts at the Electron Microscopy facility in České Budějovice, part of the Advanced Light & Electron Microscopy Prague Node, and combined advanced volumeEM technologies, including CLEM, Serial Blockface SEM, and Array Tomography.

3D models of WT *P. falciparum* parasites at different transmission stages generated using SBF-SEM.

Developing image analysis tools for studying neuroinflammation linked to COVID-19

COVID-19 infection has been associated with many neurological manifestations, from neuroinflammation to impaired brain energy metabolism. In the Turku PET Centre, which is part of Euro-BioImaging's Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node, autoradiography (ARG) is used to study brain inflammation linked to COVID-19. While ARG provides high resolution images of brain tissue, analysis of the obtained data can be very laborious. With support from the ISIDORE project, an open source analysis pipeline was developed for aligning and processing ARG images of mouse brains.

The Mouse Brain Alignment Tool (MBAT) helps to increase efficiency, accuracy and reproducibility in image registration and analysis. It was co-developed by Zuzana Čočková, a neuroscientist working at Charles University, Prague, and Junel Solis, an image analyst at Turku BioImaging, part of our Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node. The Mouse Brain Alignment Tool is open-source and available on GitHub: github.com/Turku-BioImaging/mouse-brain-alignment-tool

User interface depicting generated ROIs overlaid on the ARG section.

Multiscale multimodal 3D analysis through Phase Contrast imaging of cardiovascular alterations in a rhesus macaque monkey model for COVID-19

The direct and indirect effects of a COVID-19 infection on cardiac function are still poorly understood, especially when it comes to their interactions with pre-existing cardiac conditions, such as hypertension and heart failure. In order to understand at which scale the virus affects the cardiac tissues, PhD student Angelika Svetlove from the Max Planck Institute for Multidisciplinary Sciences in Göttingen, Germany, wanted to perform multiscale imaging of whole rhesus macaque hearts following SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The bright coherent X-Ray beam and a high propagation distance available at the SYRMEP beamline at the Elettra Synchrotron (Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node Trieste), allowed them to perform phase contrast tomography on the samples at different scales.

Ventral cardiac view in the overview scan.

PUBLICATIONS

Access to imaging services through Euro-BioImaging enables our users to collect high-quality data, which contributes to their scientific publications. Imaging core facilities, such as those that make up the Euro-BioImaging Nodes, as well as Euro-BioImaging itself, rely on researchers acknowledging the vital contributions of the experts in the imaging core facilities in their publications. We are delighted to highlight some publications from our users that were released in 2023.

In 2023,
Euro-BioImaging
Nodes
supported
2086
publications

Shadow imaging for panoptical visualization of brain tissue in vivo

Dr. Andrew Boyce, University of Calgary, Canada, contributed to a paper in Nature Communications (see caption), based on a project conducted at the French BioImaging Node funded by the Euro-BioImaging Pilot Access Fund.

Andrew Boyce with the SUSHI machine at the Bordeaux Imaging Centre (France-BioImaging). Dembitskaya, Y., Boyce, A.K.J., Idziak, A. et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42055-2>

Subcutaneous Administration of a Zwitterionic Chitosan-Based Hydrogel for Controlled Spatiotemporal Release of Monoclonal Antibodies

Francois Lux, from the University of Lyon, France, worked with the Molecular Imaging Italian Node on a study on the biodistribution, tumor uptake and excretion of a zwitterionic chitosan-based hydrogel, recently published in Advanced Materials.

Representative fluorescence images of the degradation kinetics. Gréa et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202308738>. CC BY-NC-4.0.

SorCS2 binds progranulin to regulate motor neuron development

Dr. Alena Salasova, from the Danish Research Institute of Translational Neuroscience at Aarhus University, Denmark, worked with our Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Node in Brno, Czech Republic, on this publication in Cell Reports. The beautiful full mouse embryos images were featured on the cover.

3D reconstruction of a full mouse embryo, taken from Thomasen, Pernille Bogetofte, et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2023.113333>. CC BY-NC-4.0.

Osteoporosis and COVID-19: Detected similarities in bone lacunar-level alterations via combined AI and advanced synchrotron testing

Dr. Laura Vergani, from Politecnico of Milan, Italy, contributed to this publication in Materials & Design, based on a collaboration with our Phase Contrast Imaging Node in Trieste.

Localization of the bone failure band, in the proximity of the maximum principal stresses region. Image from Buccino et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112087>. CC BY-NC-ND 4.0.

Spatiotemporal monitoring of hard tissue development reveals unknown features of tooth and bone development

Marcos Gonzalez Lopez came to visit the Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Node in Brno, Czech Republic, as a Master student and his now pursuing his PhD in Brno. His work supported by the imaging facility has been published in Science Advances.

3D imaging of mandibles taken from Gonzalez-Lopez et al, 2023. <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.adi0482>. CC BY 4.0.

A large, solid dark blue circle is positioned on the left side of a white background, extending towards the right edge. The word "INNOVATION" is centered within the blue area in white, bold, uppercase letters.

INNOVATION

TECHNOLOGY PORTFOLIO

SAMPLE CHARACTERIZATION

ELECTRON MICROSCOPY

LIGHT MICROSCOPY

ANIMAL & PLANT IMAGING

CORRELATIVE & MULTIMODAL IMAGING

IMAGE DATA ANALYSIS

HUMAN IMAGING

Euro-BiolImaging provides a large and inclusive portfolio of imaging technologies.

Innovation in imaging technologies in life sciences is continuous, fast, and exciting. To remain at the technological forefront, Euro-BiolImaging has established a work flow to ensure that new technologies are continuously integrated into our portfolio. The expert imaging facility staff at the Euro-BiolImaging Nodes are developing many new imaging methods and are making the latest developments available

in open access. We make sure that these new technologies are quality-controlled and work appropriately in open access through our Proof-of-Concept study (PCS) process. Through this process, the latest cutting-edge imaging technologies - such as MINFLUC, spatial transcriptomics and Magnetic Particle Imaging, become available to all researchers.

Technology portfolio evolution over time

NUMBER OF TECHNOLOGIES

- PROOF-OF-CONCEPT
- ACCEPTED

Today the Euro-BiolImaging technology portfolio includes 120 biological & biomedical imaging technologies and image data analysis services.

EXPANDING OUR PORTFOLIO

During 2023, three technologies have concluded the PCS process and were evaluated by our Scientific Advisory Board, before being submitted to the Euro-BioImaging Board for approval in May 2024. These technologies are in vivo Photoacoustic Imaging (PAI), Magnetoencephalography (MEG), and bimodal Optical Coherence / PhotoAcoustic Tomography (OCT/PAT).

Photoacoustic imaging (PAI)

Photoacoustic imaging is an emerging and powerful technology combining the high-contrast and the spectroscopic features of optical imaging in the near infrared region (NIR) with the high spatial-resolution and tissue penetration capability of ultrasound imaging. It is mainly used to assess vascular volume and oxygenation levels, with applications in oncology, cardiology, neurology and others. It has increased spatial resolution and penetration depth compared to optical imaging. **Now available at six Euro-BioImaging Nodes.**

PAI images of a mouse tumor region, Molecular Imaging Italian Node.

Magnetoencephalography (MEG)

Magnetoencephalography measures minute magnetic fields produced by neuronal currents of the brain. It is optimal for detecting neuronal currents at the fissural cortex of the brain offering a direct, non-invasive measure, e.g., of the primary sensory signals and epileptic discharges. **Now available at one Euro-BioImaging Node.**

MEG at the Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node, Aalto Neuroimaging.

Bimodal PAT/OCT

Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) uses scattering contrast for the reconstruction of inner structures of biological samples in vivo. It can be combined with PhotoAcoustic Tomography (PAT) or PhotoAcoustic Microscopy (PAM), giving access to complementary information. Bimodal OCT/PAT(PAM) finds application in small animal imaging and skin imaging. **Now available at one Euro-BioImaging Node.**

OCT/PAM of Zebrafish at the Austrian BioImaging Node.

In addition to the 22 technologies already undergoing Proof-of-Concept studies (PCS) during 2023, several new technologies joined their rank in 2023. These new PCS technologies are accessible at the Euro-BioImaging Nodes in open access and are being tested for their suitability for open access, technology readiness and user interest. We here highlight some of these new technologies, including two new technologies specifically answering to the increasing interest in plant imaging.

Magnetic Particle Imaging

For tracking cells and/or nanoparticles in animals and ex-vivo specimens, the CAPI Node in Prague now offers Magnetic Particle Imaging, a tomographic method based on detection of nonlinear response of superparamagnetic tracers to alternating magnetic fields.

Magnetic Particle Imaging at CAPI Node.

TeraHertz Imaging

TeraHertz Imaging consists in illuminating an object with a pulsed terahertz radiation and capturing the response through sensors in the same spectral region. The radiation is better absorbed by some molecules, like water. This technology is ideal to observe dry and very thin objects, such as leaves, dried fruits and nuts. This mobile field setup is available at the Molecular Imaging Italian Node.

Portable THz imaging, Molecular Imaging Italian Node.

Plant Phenotyping

Plant Phenotyping is designed for non-invasive, morphometric and physiological high-throughput phenotyping of small to mid-size crop plants. The PHENOPlant system at the Austria BioImaging Node is loaded with sensors: multi-excitation PAM kinetic chlorophyll fluorescence imaging, RGB, hyperspectral imaging, thermal imaging, and 3D scanning. Plants can be imaged under abiotic and biotic stress responses or treatments.

View from inside the PHENOPlant facility at the Vienna BioCenter Core Facilities.

TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT AT NODES

Random Illumination Microscopy at French BioImaging Node

The basic idea of Random Illumination Microscopy (RIM) is to use the speckle of the illumination laser in wide field to create a structured illumination pattern at the diffraction limit. By varying the pattern from image to image using a diffracting element, stacks of images can be acquired on a camera which corresponds to a cumulative homogeneous illumination.

From this we are able to reconstruct a super-resolved image at the focal plane with unprecedented optical sectioning. Marc Tramier, scientific director of MRic (Microscopy Rennes Imaging Centre), part of the Bretagne-Loire sub-Node of the French BioImaging Node, transferred the prototype from the developer lab in Toulouse to his facility and offers it as a user-friendly open access system.

RIM allows researchers to acquire super-resolved images in depth with very low amount of light at high speed, making the method very gentle for live imaging.

Comparison between confocal microscopy (bottom), airyscan (center), and RIM (top) shows a *C.elegans* with a depth $> 50\mu\text{m}$ and a spatial resolution of around 100 nm.

Portable PET Imaging for Plants at the DIMP NEUROMED Node

While you may be more familiar with positron emission tomography (PET) from medical research or hospitals, applying this nuclear imaging technology to plants allows researchers to track many aspects of plant physiology. For instance, you can quantify the fluid flow dynamics in the plants' vascular system, follow changes of CO₂ metabolism, or drought stress responses.

These kinds of observations made live and in intact plants can be very useful in understanding plant development and how they respond to the environment, particularly environmental

stress factors. Nicola D'Ascenzo and his team at the DIMP NEUROMED Node are working on developing new PET systems adapted to plants - with a particular focus on portable PET machine that can be used in the field to track short term responses of plants to environmental circumstances or treatments.

At the same time, they are also pushing the boundaries of signal processing method, with the unique capability to directly detect the dynamic evolution of noise correlations between estimated and measured variables in the PET measurements.

Nicola d'Ascenzo, DIMP NEUROMED Node, with the portable PET system prototype.

Preclinical MR Elastography at the NORMOLIM Node

In about half of patients with heart failure, the contraction of the heart chamber is relatively normal, while the filling of the heart with blood is inhibited due to stiffness of the left heart chamber. To develop improved treatments for patients with such heart stiffness, understanding how it occurs and changes is essential. The cutting-edge technique which is capable to quantify heart stiffness is MR Elastography (MRE). The University of Oslo, part of the NORMOLIM Node, demonstrates for the first time the feasibility and repeatability of cardiac MRE in rats by using a specialized cardiac MRE sequence. The results show that dynamic cardiac stiffness increases from early systole to end systole and decreases in diastole. NORMOLIM will apply MRE to rat models of various cardiac diseases to understand the mechanisms of these diseases. Simultaneously, the technique will be translated to clinical patients for disease prognosis and diagnosis.

Brillouin microscopy at Austria BioImaging

The physical properties of cells impact a broad range of cellular processes, including metastatic potential, but measuring cellular mechanics without disrupting the cells is a complex task. Kareem Elsayad and his team at the Center for Anatomy and Cell Biology, a part of the Medical Imaging Cluster at MedUni Vienna within the Austrian BioImaging Node, are applying Brillouin Light Scattering to image intricate mechanical features within the cell nucleus, all in real-time and within living cells. This method relies on the scattering of light from thermal vibrations in the sample and can allow the scientists to calculate the sample's elasticity and viscosity.

As the method uses the interaction of light directly with the sample, the cells to be measure do not have to be specifically prepared, labelled or placed on specific substrates.

Magnitude images and stiffness maps from a representative rat (Unpublished data from Lisa Smith, IEMF, OUS, Norway).

The Brillouin Light Scattering Microscopy setup at the Center for Anatomy and Cell Biology, MedUni Vienna (Austrian Biomedicine/CMi Node)

Micro-PIXE at SiMBION Node

In-air PIXE developments by the imaging facility at Jožef Stefan Institute, part of our SiMBION Node. To learn more, read the paper: Isaković et al, A parallel-beam wavelength-dispersive X-ray emission spectrometer for high energy resolution in-air micro-PIXE analysis, *Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry*, Volume 38, Issue 5, Pages 1164 - 1172/13 April 2023. Above image is Figure 2 from Isaković et al, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3JA00019B>. CC BY-NC 3.0.

CT Imaging at the Phase Contrast Flagship Node Trieste

Imaging organs inside patients with the aim of detecting developing diseases faces many challenges. “Synchrotron radiation-based phase contrast imaging (SRCT) is capable of very high spatial and temporal resolutions. It is therefore extremely useful for studying lesions, cancer nodules or fibrosis,” explains Giuliana Tromba, from our Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node at the Elettra Synchrotron in Trieste.

The unique properties of SRCT make it an interesting target to use in medical imaging applications. Christian Dullin, an expert in preclinical studies at the University Medical Center Göttingen, has been collaborating with Giuliana Tromba for over 5 years, to push the resolution limit in phase contrast imaging on

phantom lung models. Their newest setup results in high-resolution tomographic images with 7x better details and 2-3 times less exposure than traditional CT. This means that the setup allows for ex vivo imaging of intact human organs, such as the lung, at clinical relevant X-Ray dose levels that would allow to further translate the technology to patients.

The set-up is based on a novel custom-made human-size chest based on a pig lung phantom model to test and develop these imaging applications further. A specific example of where this setup could be a game-changer is in detecting the early formation of lung fibrosis, not visible in conventional CT.

Lung imaging setup at the beam line, including the specially-designed positioning stage and resulting higher resolution. Figure from Dullin et al., *European Respiratory Journal*, 2024. <https://erj.ersjournals.com/content/63/3/2301604>. CC BY 4.0.

TECHNOLOGIES OF THE YEAR

In the graphic below, we are pleased to report on the most requested technologies at Euro-Biolmaging between 2022 and 2023. Data source is the Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal (EWP).

TOP 4 MOST REQUESTED TECHNOLOGIES

BIOLOGICAL IMAGING

- | | | | | | | | |
|----------|------------------------|----------|----------------------------------|----------|---------------------------------|----------|---|
| 1 | Confocal
Microscopy | 2 | Volume
Electron
Microscopy | 3 | cryo-
Electron
Tomography | 4 | Single Molecule
Localisation
Microscopy |
|----------|------------------------|----------|----------------------------------|----------|---------------------------------|----------|---|

BIOMEDICAL IMAGING

- | | | | | | | | |
|----------|----------------------------------|----------|--------|----------|------------------------------|----------|-------------------------------|
| 1 | Magnetic
Resonance
Imaging | 2 | PET/CT | 3 | Phase
Contrast
Imaging | 4 | in vivo
Optical
Imaging |
|----------|----------------------------------|----------|--------|----------|------------------------------|----------|-------------------------------|

Volume EM - Spotlight Technology 2023

Selected by Nature as one of seven "Technologies to watch in 2023" volume Electron Microscopy (vEM) in its various implementations has been growing as an increasingly widely requested and available imaging technology. The interest is understandable, as it provides the ultrastructural resolution of Electron Microscopy in larger volumes, including entire cells and beyond.

Through Euro-Biolmaging six different types of vEM are accessible to researchers at 14 Euro-Biolmaging Nodes.

Image by Ilya Belevich, University of Helsinki, FiAM Node

**DATA
SERVICES**

IMAGE DATA ANALYSIS AT NODES

To support production of quality data, analysis methods and an extended data life cycle, Euro-BiolImaging offers Image Data Services for the benefit of the whole imaging community. Together with our expert Nodes staff, we support adoption of practices that yield FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) image data and analysis workflows. In addition to directly supporting users with analysis of their data, many of the Bioimage Analysts at our Nodes are involved in developing and actively maintaining Open image analysis tools and libraries, which serve Euro-BiolImaging users as well as the global scientific community.

227

staff members provide image analysis and image data management services at Euro-BiolImaging Nodes.

Christophe Avenel in discussion with the BIIF team (NMI Sweden).

17

requests for biological and biomedical image data analysis as a stand-alone service in 2023.

Image Data Analyst Junel Solis, Turku BioImaging, consults with a user (FiAM Node).

10+

Nodes provided Image Data Analysis services as part of our PCS in 2023.

Brainstorm session. Photo courtesy of Population Imaging Node, Rotterdam.

IMAGE DATA SERVICES FOR USERS

Since 2022, Euro-BioImaging offers its users Image Data Analysis (IDA) as a standalone service for image data irrespective of where it was acquired. Below is a compelling example of how Euro-BioImaging Nodes offer Image Data Analysis as a service.

Case study: Image Data Analysis Service

Michaela Blažíková is a Bioimage Analyst at the Institute of Molecular Genetics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, part of Euro-BioImaging's Advanced Light & Electron Microscopy Node in Prague.

In September 2022, Michaela took up an IDA project to support the research of Shiladitya Mitra from the Max Planck Institute for Psychiatry in Germany who was working on mice stress and behavior analysis. Shiladitya had a big collection of mouse brain images from his home institute acquired with a light-sheet microscope that they wanted to share on the Allen Brain Atlas. When he contacted Michaela, the data acquisition and pre-processing had already been accomplished: the clearing of mice brains and imaging was done at MPI and the data were already stitched and fused. The problem was that for final analysis and annotation, Shiladitya and his team planned to use an already published analysis pipeline based

on specific tools, know-how and hardware they didn't have ready access to.

At our Prague Node, Michaela had the right computational skills, software licenses, know-how, and access to high performance computing power needed to finalize the project.

The project was completed in October 2023.

Michaela and Shiladitya presented their results at the Euro-BioImaging User Forum on "Image Data". Their presentation underscored the benefits of outsourcing part of a complex project.

Scan to watch the presentation of the Image Data Analysis Service case study

What is image data analysis as a stand-alone service?

Our Euro-BioImaging Nodes can provide users a variety of biological and biomedical image data analysis services including:

- Image denoising, registration, segmentation, tracking, and many other image analysis procedures applied to a wide variety of image datasets
- Data workflows, bespoke analysis tools including implementation of machine learning methods
- Access to high performance computing and specialised software

FAIR IMAGE DATA

Euro-BioImaging supports the development of a FAIR bioimage data ecosystem. We offer guidelines, training and direct support for producing open, FAIR Image data. Scientific data needs to be created with longevity in mind to follow the digital transition. The FAIR principles accelerate scientific progress by enabling data to be more readily incorporated into research projects, improving transparency and boosting scientific collaborations.

BioImaging Communities' Path to FAIR

Euro-BioImaging has published a review article on “Building a FAIR image data ecosystem for microscopy communities” in the journal *Histochemistry and Cell Biology*. It highlights the many efforts and solutions to address the challenges on the road to FAIR bioimage data that are currently being developed by the microscopy community and summarises how different stakeholders, including Research Infrastructures, are shaping the FAIR data ecosystem. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-023-02203-7>

Establishing Image Data Stewardship

Within the BY-COVID project (Grant Agreement # 101046203), our FAIR Image Data Steward drives the mobilisation of infectious disease datasets from our Nodes to the bioimaging repositories. Our Data Steward provides one-on-one guidance in all stages of the data lifecycle, from project planning to data deposition. In this way we reduce the barriers and streamline the deposition process, resulting in more datasets for potential reuse.

This figure represents the six facets of FAIR bioimaging data coupled with the approaches and tools under active development by the community. Further improving all of these areas still requires awareness, incentives, and rewards to move toward the ultimate goal of FAIR bioimaging data. (Kemmer et al., 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-023-02203-7>. CC BY)

Providing training on FAIR data

In March 2023, we held our first online training on FAIR data. This open workshop provided over 100 participants easy steps towards FAIR bioimage data and highlighted user success stories. We showcased various bioimage data repositories and gave an outlook on latest community developments supported by Euro-BioImaging such as AI-ready datasets and next-generation file formats.

BIOIMAGE DATA REPOSITORIES

As one cornerstone of FAIR data, Euro-Biolmaging strongly encourages data sharing through dedicated bioimage repositories. To this end, we are supporting and shaping the existing ecosystem of open archives and developing solutions in areas of need.

Support for Open Bioimage Repositories

Euro-Biolmaging works closely with various dedicated bioimage data repositories, mediating user interaction and influx of quality data. In particular our data steward works towards improving data deposition pathways which allows for a more seamless and straightforward uptake of data from the community. At Euro-Biolmaging's initiative, the BioImage Archive has made it possible to credit data stewards involved in supporting dataset submission. This is an important step towards recognizing the time and effort that goes into ensuring high data quality.

BioImage Archive

Developing a repository for preclinical metadata - PIDAR

The Preclinical Image DATaset Repository (PIDAR) is a public repository of metadata information describing preclinical image datasets from any imaging modality. Hosted by the University of Turin, it catalogs pre-clinical datasets associated with peer-reviewed publications. PIDAR aims to improve the FAIRness of preclinical image datasets through improved discoverability and curation. The imaging metadata are organized as “collections” defined by a common disease, image modality or sub type (MRI, CT, PET, etc) or research focus, through structured metadata models curated with selected ontologies.

<https://pidar.hpc4ai.unito.it/>

Data sharing showcase: Making SARS-CoV-2 imaging data openly available

Using imaging on reconstituted bronchial epithelia from adult and child donors, performed at the Bordeaux Imaging Center, French BioImaging Node, Guillaume Beucher from Harald Wodrich's team described a unique mechanism of spread of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Through a collaboration of our data steward with the group's engineer, Nicolas Landrein, the full dataset comprising widefield, confocal and electron microscopy of SARS-CoV-2 infected lung tissue was deposited to the BioImage Archive. Using the community-developed metadata standard REMBI, the dataset is now reusable for future research on SARS-CoV-2 and similar diseases.

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/Biolimages/studies/S-BIAD677>

SARS-CoV-2 dataset shared in the BioImage Archive.

HIGHLIGHT: IMAGE DATA IN THE CLOUD

For efficient image data management and analysis, large and complex datasets require specialised solutions, including those supported by cloud resources. Euro-BioImaging, supported by European projects, provides technical solutions for cloud compatible image data formats and workflows for the global community.

BatchConvert: A versatile solution for high-throughput parallelized conversion of image data to open formats.

BatchConvert is a performant command line tool that facilitates conversion of image data collections to either of the standard open formats OME-TIFF or OME-Zarr. Built upon the workflow orchestrator Nextflow, BatchConvert commands trigger concurrent workflows that couple the conversion process to data transfer.

BatchConvert readily runs on Slurm-managed HPC clusters, which requires the user to specify only a single command line argument. Other features of BatchConvert include support for multiple modes of conversion and extensive options for input data filtering.

As such, local and remote data storage can be specified as the input source or the output destination, saving the user the upload/download processes. This also allows the user to submit the output datasets automatically to the BioImage Archive.

The architecture of BatchConvert. BatchConvert was developed by Euro-BioImaging Image Data Specialist Bugra Özdemir, as part of our work in the EOSC Future project (GA #101017536).

The user can parameterize the conversion workflow by either passing arguments directly to the command line or using a separate interactive configuration step. Once the command is run, Nextflow consumes the parameters to generate and execute the workflow, which handles the data conversion and, optionally, the data transfer to and from the remote storage.

BatchConvert

<https://github.com/Euro-BioImaging/BatchConvert>
<https://anaconda.org/Euro-BioImaging/batchconvert>

BatchConvert

NGFF community

<https://doi.org/10.3897/arphapreprints.e116669>
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-023-02209-1>

OUTREACH

COMMUNITY

Euro-BioImaging works closely with an extensive and varied network of stakeholders. This puts us in a unique position to foster a strong, interdisciplinary collaboration environment striving towards open science. Through our actions with different stakeholders, we are involved in a number of activities that bring added-value for research, innovation, and technology and strengthen the overall competitiveness of the European Research Area - and beyond. In the next pages, discover some of the ways in which we interact with our stakeholders.

STAKEHOLDERS OF EURO-BIOIMAGING AN OVERVIEW

In 2023, we engaged with the scientific community at a record number of conferences & community events. We also visited our Nodes and presented Euro-BioImaging at Node events. We participated in Hackathons and contributed to training courses with potential users. We met with policy makers and European stakeholders at high-level policy events and engaged with our Research Infrastructure partners at EU-funded project meetings. In addition, Euro-BioImaging organized a number of online events for key stakeholders, namely Nodes, users,

researchers, and members of the biological and biomedical imaging communities. We also engaged with Node staff, researchers and industry colleagues via our Expert Groups. In addition, we contributed to events organized by the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board and developed our international relations by working with stakeholders in Latin America, Australia, and in Africa via Global BioImaging. In these pages of the Annual Report, we present some highlights of the year.

140 Biolmaging UK and Euro Biolmaging

Johanna Bischof and UK Node manager Georgina Fletcher at mmc2023 in Manchester, UK.

John Eriksson presents the Euro-Biolmaging technology portfolio at the Bridging Cancer Frontiers event in Turku, Finland.

Rafael Diaz and Marcela Rivera talk about Euro-Biolmaging with students at the Organ on a Chip conference in Helsinki, Finland.

Austrian Biolmaging Director, Baubak Bajoghli, hosted Euro-Biolmaging Med-Hub & Bio-Hub Section directors and Med-Hub colleagues in Vienna in March 2023.

EMIM 2023 in Salzburg, Austria.

Susanne Vainio and Alessandra Viale at WMIC in Prague.

Johanna Bischof presents Euro-Biolmaging at the Congress of the Brazilian Society of Microscopy and Microanalysis in Brazil.

Euro-Biolmaging Hub team, France-Biolmaging and Israel Biolmaging Node staff at the ANERIS meeting in Barcelona, Spain.

Euro-Biolmaging had a booth with NL-Biolmaging at ELMI 2023 in Noordwijkerhout, The Netherlands, complete with a visit from Antonie van Leeuwenhoek.

Conferences & Meetings

37

Community conferences & events

12

Policy events

8

Node visits & events

4

Training events

20

EU project meetings

OUR EVENTS

Euro-BiolImaging organises a number of online events that are free and open to the community. In 2023, attendance at our online events soared, as you will see on p.53 in our Digital Communications overview.

Virtual Pub

In 2023, Euro-BiolImaging continued to organize the online Virtual Pub events, a free weekly lecture series, open to the entire imaging community. Topics include new biological and biomedical imaging technologies, image analysis, and other topics of interest to the imaging community. In 2023, we organised Virtual Pubs once a month in collaboration with the volumeEM community and the COMULISglobe community. We also organised five Special Edition Virtual Pubs on topics like Open Hardware, Infectious Diseases, and Image Data Analysis.

User Forum

Designed to highlight the importance of imaging to different research areas, the Euro-BiolImaging User Forum takes place twice a year and features keynote presentations from prominent scientists as well as presentations from users at our Nodes. In 2023, we explored how imaging supports cardiovascular research and plant biology. Both events attracted researchers, students, core facility staff, policy makers and industry representatives. We were pleased that the 'Understanding Plant Biology' event also attracted members of the AgroServ project consortium.

Scan to watch the Virtual Pub and User Forum recordings.

The Virtual Pub in 2023

14

Presentations from the Nodes
(incl. Special Editions)

5

Special Edition
of the Virtual Pub

5

Correlative Imaging series talks with COMULISglobe

5

Volume EM series talks with the vEM community

39

Events
during 2023

INDUSTRY RELATIONS

The Euro-BioImaging Industry Board (EBIB) continued and intensified its close collaboration with Euro-BioImaging throughout 2023. Companies in the field of imaging that are represented on the Board are joined together by their recognition of the importance that coordinated open access imaging platforms play in strengthening research in Europe. Through the EBIB, companies gain facilitated access to information about the latest trends in imaging, international imaging communities including other technology developers and providers, and imaging-associated opportunities. Facilities find a single entry point to showcase their own developments to industry, express their imaging needs, and find partners for different types of collaborations. And the EBIB keeps on growing - with Telight, which joined as the 16th member this year. Below are just a few highlights of EBIB's interactions with the Euro-BioImaging community this year.

Tech Exchange

In our webinar series for latest technology developments in industry, we saw 14 presentations from innovative companies in the imaging field, including 5 EBIB members, on a range of topics and across scales from super-resolution to preclinical application of hyperpolarized MRI. Presentations were well appreciated by our audience, with on average 57 attendees per session.

Smart Microscopy Working Group

Following the success of the thematic workshop in autumn 2022, a working group was set up to address microscopy workflow challenges with a team of experts from facilities and industry. The group now meets monthly to present new developments and discuss innovative solutions. The work of the group was presented at ELMI 2023, leading to an influx of new members, and resulted in a joint funding application for future developments.

Industry and European projects

Collaborations with industry provide substantial mutual benefits – and through regular exchange during EBIB meetings, we were able to inform our partners of opportunities to participate and collaborate in various EU projects: pre-commercial procurement opportunities for the development of Transmission Electron Microscopy technology in IMPRESS; participation in expert groups and trainings for remote access and operations of imaging instruments in eRImote; consultation on beta-testing and technology validation with facilities in IMAGINE or accessing ML and AI models for image analysis for integration into proprietary software via AI4Life.

In a collaboration that was facilitated by the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board, AI4Life project (coordinated by Euro-BioImaging) and Leica Microsystems have joined forces to help researchers leverage AI methods for analysis of complex image data. Models curated by the BioImage Model Zoo are recognized directly in AIVIA image analysis software.

Meeting the imaging community at eye-level

April 2023 saw the first in-person Euro-BioImaging All-hands Nodes meeting, followed by a back-to-back Industry Board-organised workshop on “BioImaging and the European Open Science Cloud.” The Industry Board Coordinator successfully applied for financial support for this event through the EOSC-Life project, which supported this mutual exchange. The well-defined workshop concept and the high interest in the topic, demonstrated by the participation of more than 85 participants from academia, industry, science journals and policy makers both on site and online, persuaded the project coordinators to fully fund this event, including covering the travel costs for all speakers from the EOSC community and the Industry Board. Mixed sessions and the many networking opportunities during the two meetings helped build trust and lasting relationships between the participants from the Euro-BioImaging Nodes and the EBIB partners.

Attendees at the BioImaging and the European Open Science Cloud workshop in April 2023.

Outlook

Building strong partnerships with industry remains one of Euro-BioImaging’s strategic goals for its next 5-year cycle. This will benefit focus areas such as image data management and training that play an important role for both partners. In 2024, the Euro-BioImaging Industry Board will also celebrate its 10th anniversary, illustrating the long-term commitment of our industry partners.

“

The new Five Years strategic plan was excellently developed by the Directorate of Euro-BioImaging. It’s a great guideline to further strengthen our interactions in the future - for example intensifying our collaboration between industry and the community on modern training technology.

Herbert Schaden
Euro-BioImaging Industry Board Chair

EUROPEAN STAKEHOLDERS

Euro-BioImaging is an active actor in the European research policy landscape - through its participation in ERIC Forum, EOSC Association, and support for diverse policy initiatives. Here we highlight some of the relevant policy meetings and initiatives from 2023.

Euro-BioImaging supports the Lund Declaration

Research Data as a resource, as well as a challenge, unites the research landscape - therefore, Euro-BioImaging joined European leaders and Research Infrastructure representatives for a high-level conference in Lund, Sweden on “The Potential of Research Data: How Research Infrastructures Provide New Opportunities and Benefits for Society.” This conference, initiated by the Swedish presidency of the EU, explored the opportunities and challenges linked to collaboration on open data and highlighted the essential role of Research

Infrastructures in the digital era.

It culminated in the publication of the Lund Declaration, a document which places the responsibility to promote FAIR data generation and sharing to improve Europe’s competitiveness on the shoulders of Research Infrastructures like Euro-BioImaging ERIC.

Through our Image Data Services and the active experts at our Nodes, we are ready to take up this responsibility. Director General John Eriksson was part of the panel discussion.

John Eriksson, part of panel discussion on data sharing in Lund, Sweden.

Euro-BioImaging contributes to the EOSC Association

Underscoring our commitment to FAIR data and data sharing, Euro-BioImaging is also an active member of the EOSC Association since 2021. In 2022 and 2023 we also acted as mandated organization for the ERIC Forum, representing the voices of all ERICs who are members in the EOSC Association in the EOSC Association meetings.

Euro-BioImaging provides regular input in the Multi-Annual Roadmap and actively contributes in various EOSC Association Task Forces. In 2023 we also participated in a number of related working groups, such as the ESFRI-EOSC Working Group.

The importance of the Tenerife Declaration

Between September 25-26, Euro-BioImaging Hub members including Antje Keppler as the current Chair of ERIC Forum, attended and contributed to the Research Infrastructures event under the auspices of the Spanish Council presidency in Tenerife. Three main topics were discussed: Sustainability, global dimension of ERICs and science diplomacy. Global BioImaging was presented as an excellent example of how European RIs can foster successful global collaborations and advance science diplomacy. The meeting concluded in the Tenerife Declaration, which is supported by Euro-BioImaging.

Antje Keppler, part of panel discussion on Research Infrastructures in Tenerife, Spain.

INTERNATIONAL STAKEHOLDERS

Building on the connections facilitated by Global BioImaging (GBI), Euro-BioImaging was honored to be invited to the Congress of the Brazilian Society of Microscopy and Microanalysis. There we hosted alongside Latin America BioImaging, SBMM, CEBEM, and GBI a highly successful pre-congress workshop on "Bridging Borders in BioImaging".

Furthermore, Euro-BioImaging participates as a supporting partner in the RI-Hubs projects, which launched in April 2023, funded by the EU-LAC interest group, together with Instruct ERIC. In this project our PPBI and Italian ALM Nodes are collaborating with partners in Latin America, including in Uruguay, Brazil, and Peru through training courses and staff exchanges. In addition, Euro-BioImaging was among 8 European RIs that met with representatives from the Australian National Research Infrastructures (NCRIS) in September 2023 in Italy to discuss common

priorities & challenges for infrastructures in the health domain and identify opportunities for collaboration. The Euro-BioImaging directorate was invited to attend and Antje Keppler, in her role as ERIC Forum Chair, co-hosted the symposium alongside her Australian counterpart Ian Smith.

Finally, like every year, the Global BioImaging Exchange of Experience meeting is a highlight of the year. In 2023, it was co-organised with the South Africa BioImaging Community (SABI) and the Africa BioImaging Consortium (ABIC) and was held in Stellenbosch and Cape Town in South Africa. The meeting focussed on "Empowering Imaging Scientists through Training" and brought together 192 participants from 48 different countries, including strong participation from Euro-BioImaging and its Nodes, particularly France BioImaging, NMI Sweden, and Portuguese BioImaging Platform (PPBI).

Africa: Global Imaging's Exchange of Experience 2023 in Cape Town and Stellenbosch University (bottom, across).

Latin America: SBMM Congress in Brazil (right) and RI Hubs meeting (below, left. Photo by @ red_cebem on X)

Australia: Attendees at the Australian RIs event in Prato, Italy. (below, right. Photo by @ EMBLaustralia on X)

EXPERT GROUPS

Euro-BiolImaging runs a number of Expert Groups where Node staff, community experts, and industry partners come together around topics of interest. Here we feature two of our most recent Expert Groups.

Plant Imaging Expert Group

This group addresses rising interest in applying imaging techniques to plant biology questions and utilising them to understand and impact agroecological processes. The Plant Imaging Expert Group is chaired by Nicola D'Ascenzo from the DIMP NEUROMED Node and Marc van Zandvoort from the AMMI Maastricht Node, and brings together plant imaging experts and plant scientists interested in using imaging techniques in their research from across the Euro-BiolImaging community. The represented techniques range from Electron Microscopy and MassSpec Imaging, to Light Microscopy, Plant Phenotyping, Terahertz Imaging, and PET and MRI applications for plants.

The group holds a regular seminar series to introduce the diverse technologies and their applications in plant imaging, as well as coming together for joint grant applications and review paper preparation.

Did you know?

A number of Expert Groups on varied topics are available. Check them on our website!

<https://eurobioimaging.eu/expert-groups/>

FAIR Image Workflows

Although there are tools and workflows available for analyzing image data, they are scattered across different research fields and locations. The goal of this Expert Group is to encourage collaboration among people who are interested in improving the usability and accessibility of image data workflows, regardless of their scientific or technical background.

DIGITAL COMMUNICATIONS

Online communication channels continued to be an important way to reach our stakeholders in 2023. We used social media, primarily Twitter and LinkedIn, to interact with a variety of partners, give visibility to imaging scientists and our Nodes, promote breakthroughs in imaging research, and advertise our online events. We increased our followers on YouTube in 2023 by sharing content from events organised as part of our participation in EU-funded projects like eRImote (Grant Agreement #101057557) and ANERIS (Grant Agreement #101094924) as well as by continuing to record and share Virtual Pub and User Forum talks. We continued to use social media channels as well as our regular newsletters to drive traffic to our website. Thanks to increased visibility of our online channels, attendance at our online events soared. Below are our key numbers from January 2020 to January 2024.

WEBSITE

534,759

Page views since ERIC creation

SOCIAL MEDIA

NEWSLETTER

3

Regular newsletters -
to three target audiences

5,000+

Cumulative recipients
including Nodes,
RI partners & Governance

36%

Average open rate for
campaigns in 2022—2023

PARTICIPATION IN EURO-BIOIMAGING ONLINE EVENTS

USER FORUM

1,000

Participants

6

Events

VIRTUAL PUB

7,594

Participants

142

Events

 = 100 PEOPLE

A large, dark blue circular graphic is positioned on the left side of a white background, partially overlapping the edge. The text 'FUNDED PROJECTS' is centered within the blue area.

**FUNDED
PROJECTS**

OVERVIEW

In 2023, Euro-Biolmaging ERIC continued to lead and contribute to a wide range of EU-funded projects. In the next pages, discover the projects Euro-Biolmaging is involved in and how they benefit our stakeholders and community.

Representation of Euro-Biolmaging project involvement in 2023.

2023 marked the kick-off for a new generation of big EU-funded consortia projects dedicated to the development of new technologies and their dissemination to the research community through the Research Infrastructures - the INFRA-TECH projects. Euro-Biolmaging is involved in three INFRA-TECH projects - IMAGINE, ANERIS, IMPRESS - that started this year. At the same time, Euro-Biolmaging continued to provide access to its portfolio of cutting-edge imaging technologies to researchers in different domains through the INFRA-SERV projects - see for example the ISIDORe-supported user projects featured in these pages in our IMPACT section. The Euro-Biolmaging coordinated project AI4Life continued to create waves in 2023 - with open calls, hackathons, and supported research

projects. We also marked the conclusion of the EOSC-Life project, which has been connecting life science researchers to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) since 2019 by making tools and research data cloud-compatible and accessible to all.

Together with our Nodes, we are also actively participating in one of the Digital program projects that started this year, EUCAIM, aiming at building a federated infrastructure for cancer image data. In 2023 we also celebrate the granting of two new EU INFRA-DEV projects - foundingGIDE and EVOLVE - that are described in our ACHIEVEMENTS section and complement our growing and constantly evolving project landscape.

OUR PROJECTS

USER ACCESS PROJECTS

canSERV
providing cutting edge
cancer research services
across europe

Euro-BiolImaging provides access to a large range of cutting-edge imaging technologies and expert support, but to ensure equitable access, we are always working to provide funding that allows researchers to access these services free of charge.

In this regard, the EU-funded INFRA-SERV projects are a great resource. The INFRA-SERV projects bring together large consortia of Research Infrastructures that make their services available to researchers. The consortia receive funding from the EU that allow these services to be provided free of charge to the researchers while the experts and service providers at the Nodes receive fair compensation. The grouping of different Infrastructures in these consortia also allows for the provision of integrated services from different domains - combining, for instance, imaging services from Euro-BiolImaging with murine animal models of disease from INFRAFRONTIER ERIC, or with plant screening services from EMPHASIS ERIC.

The ISIDORe project, supporting infectious disease research, kicked off in February 2022 and was running full steam in 2023. Some examples of research projects supported by the ISIDORe project at Euro-BiolImaging Nodes are featured in the IMPACT section of our Annual Report. Here are some key numbers explaining how ISIDORe has supported user projects at Euro-BiolImaging Nodes so far.

In 2023, the first Open Calls also launched in canSERV and AgroServ. These projects will continue to provide ongoing opportunities for funded user access in 2024 and beyond. All researchers are encouraged to take advantage of these opportunities!

In AgroServ, user projects have to include services from at least two Research Infrastructures to facilitate the development of an integrated service provision for agroecology research. During the 1st AgroServ Call for expressions of interest, Euro-BiolImaging received about 20% of all pre-proposal applications and our services were requested in conjunction with the services from most consortium partners, such as AnaEE, EU-OPENSREEN, EMPHASIS, MIRRI, EMBRC, and ELIXIR, showing the broad applicability of imaging services.

Amount of proposals received per RI and the connections to other RI in the same proposal in AgroServ.

ISIDORe Overview

19 user projects at
7 Nodes
343K€ TNA budget

including travel grants &
free biological resources
supporting user projects.

DATA PROJECTS

In 2023, AI4Life launched our first open call, receiving 72 applications and ultimately selecting 8 projects. A list of services provided by AI4Life is now available on our project website. We also published the MIFA preprint, offering valuable recommendations for image annotations to enhance AI-ready datasets.

Our year was filled with numerous workshops, hackathons, and active participation in various conferences.

In November-December 2023, Euro-BioImaging organized in collaboration with its Nodes France BioImaging and Israel BioImaging a three-part workshop series to explore the realms of AI application for image processing as part of the ANERIS project. These workshops, featuring speakers from Life, Marine and Computer science communities, entitled “AI Basics for Image Processing” drew substantial attendance with over 400 participants and provided them with both theoretical introductions as well as practical demos of specific AI tools, garnering lots of positive feedback.

AI4Life factsheet 2023 (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10257243)

AI4Life News

<https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/news/>

Newsletter sign-up

<https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/newsletter/>

Scan to check the sessions on the Euro-BioImaging YouTube channel

During the course of its four and half years, the EOSC-Life project (eosc-life.eu) supported many user projects through Open Calls and expert support, as well as by facilitating the sharing of data and research tools and resources interoperable in the cloud. To draw from the spectrum of outputs and experiences across disciplines in Life Sciences, the EOSC-Life consortium partners concluded the project with a landmark publication in the EMBO Journal, “Be sustainable”: EOSC-Life recommendations for implementation of FAIR principles in life science data handling” (<https://doi.org/10.15252/embj.2023115008>) with co-authoring contributions from the Euro-Biolmaging Hub Team and imaging community. This work refers to lessons learned from cross-disciplinary, community-driven, and competitively selected projects supported through EOSC-Life, and presents key findings, procedures, effective measures, and recommendations that can be used to generate and establish sustainable life science research resources in the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). It also highlights how Life Science communities in the Open Science framework urgently need to increase the sustainability and re-use of data resources, software tools, and workflows, especially when conducting large-scale data-driven research and computational analyses.

European Federation for Cancer IMages (EUCAIM) aims at deploying a federated infrastructure of cancer images, making them available to clinicians, researchers, and innovators. It will allow for the development, benchmarking, testing, and piloting of Artificial Intelligence-based technologies for cancer diagnosis and treatment. The consortium consist of 76 partners from 14 countries. Several partners are also part of the AI4Health Imaging initiative or major European Research Infrastructures (such as Euro-Biolmaging, BBMRI, EATRIS and ELIXIR). Euro-Biolmaging is proud to participate in the project alongside several of its Nodes: DIMP NEUROMED, the Portuguese Brain Imaging Network (University of Coimbra), as well as the Population Imaging Flagship Node Rotterdam (ERASMUS MC) and MMMI Italian Node (IRCSS SDN). The EUCAIM project is a flagship of Europe’s Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP), and coordinated by Prof. Luis Marti-Bonmati who is leading one of the new Spanish nodes: Population Imaging Valencia. Euro-Biolmaging and its Nodes contribute to a number of Work Packages to help build the backbone for the next generation of cancer diagnostics and treatments. In October 2023, the EUCAIM consortium announced the first public release of its platform, marking a major milestone in the project’s development and an exciting step towards achieving its vision and goals.

Illustration of the EOSC-Life project positioning within the LS RIs ecosystem and the EOSC landscape.
<https://www.eosc-life.eu/achievements/recommendations-for-fair-resources-in-life-sciences-research/>

PERSPECTIVES

PERSPECTIVES

In 2023, Euro-BioImaging took significant steps towards building its future. Developed and approved during 2023, the Strategic Plan for 2024-2028 materialises Euro-BioImaging's ambition to advance the forefront of European science. Articulated around six objectives, the plan is designed to strengthen Euro-BioImaging's structural operability, deepen the infrastructure's relations with all its stakeholders and support and connect the European imaging landscape. Through pursuing these strategic objectives, Euro-BioImaging is steadfast in its commitment to promoting research excellence and fostering innovation in Europe.

The Strategic Plan was designed with a greater impact in mind. The six strategic goals are not one-sided but bidirectional: their achievement will benefit Euro-BioImaging and the imaging community as a whole. The Strategic Plan for 2024-2028 envisions a future where imaging plays a pivotal role in sustaining, enabling, and advancing science.

This will be achieved by enhancing the accessibility and capacity of the imaging infrastructure, championing Open Science, expanding the services available to researchers, increasing awareness, communicating impact of imaging, and fostering stronger collaborations with industry and academia.

Our Strategic Plan engages all our diverse stakeholder groups and lays a solid foundation for the next five years of Euro-BioImaging activities.

Scan to read more about the Strategy Plan 2024-2028

Overview of the six Euro-Bioimaging strategic goals for 2024-2028

**FINANCIAL
INFORMATION**

FINANCIAL INFORMATION

The income and expenses for the financial year 2023 and the reserve funds are outlined in Table 1. Received in-kind contributions and costs booked to project funding sources are presented in Table 2. Euro-Biolmaging ERIC's accounts are audited every year according to Finnish law.

Income Statement and Reserve Funds for the financial year January 1 - December 31, 2023 (table 1)

INCOME (in Euros)	
Income	
Membership Contributions	1,584,043
Other	83,156
Expenses	
Personnel Cost	-1,282,474
Services, consultation, outsourcing	-182,566
Meetings and events	-108,270
Depreciation	0
Travel	-119,689
Euro-Biolmaging Web Portal (EWP)	-93,837
Other (computer equipment, software and licenses, fees, shipping, and exchange rate fluctuation costs)	-58,641
User Access Funding	-37,037
Net Financial Result	-215,316
RESERVE FUNDS (in Euros)	
Reserve, January 1, 2023	2,122,587
Net Financial Result 2023	-215,316
Reserve, December 31, 2023	1,907,270

Table 2. External funding sources for the financial year January 1 - December 31, 2023 (table 2)

EXTERNAL FUNDING (in Euros)	
In-kind (FTE)	0.7 FTE
Costs booked to external project funding (€)	-797,148

**FROM
OUR NODES**

OVERVIEW

Euro-BiolMaging is a distributed infrastructure - our central activities are coordinated by our three Hub sites, but services are provided in the imaging facilities called 'Nodes'. By becoming a Euro-BiolMaging Node, imaging facilities agree to provide open access to technologies, services and expertise to all Euro- BiolMaging users, independent of where the users come from, their field of research or their level of expertise.

To become a Euro-BiolMaging Node, facilities go through a rigorous application and review process in the Call for Nodes. They are evaluated by our Scientific Advisory Board on a wide variety of factors, including:

- Scientific and technical excellence
- European and national significance
- Technology maintenance and updates
- Access and service package
- Quality assurance
- User training
- Other technology-specific factors

Following successful evaluation and approval by the Board, the Nodes join the Euro-BiolMaging family by signing service level agreements that outline the services to Euro-BiolMaging users.

After an intense period of growth between 2020 to 2022, in 2023, our Node family remained stable. In January 2024, we welcomed 6 new Nodes in Spain and in Belgium, our new member states, and more Node upgrades follow in 2024 arising from the Call for Node Upgrades launched in November 2023.

In addition to supporting user projects, our Nodes are active in European-funded research projects, support and develop technological breakthroughs, organise outstanding training courses and conferences, and make science accessible to the public through their outreach efforts.

They also engage in teaching on the Master's and PhD levels and get kids inspired by STEM subjects through hands-on imaging experiences.

In the following pages, discover just some of the activities that are taking place at our Nodes, as well as the new instruments they are offering in open access to support scientific advancement in the European Research Area and beyond.

Flying the Euro-BiolMaging colors at the Microscopy Innovation Centre, King's College London, part of our UK Node.

“

Working for the Population Imaging Flagship Node gives us the opportunity to bring solutions to the European imaging community, widening our audience and increasing our impact.

Hakim Achterberg
Research Software Engineer,
Population Imaging Node Rotterdam

TRAINING

With the advances in imaging technology, more and more new technologies are available to users, making training in the correct use of the technologies and the connected sample preparation and data analysis crucial. The Euro-BioImaging Nodes offer a wide range of training opportunities.

Training opportunities at Euro-BioImaging Nodes cover the full spectrum of technologies available from biological to biomedical imaging as well as sample preparation and handling, and image data analysis. Some courses are taught remotely and virtually, increasing their accessibility. As a general rule, the courses combine theory and hands-on learning. The training courses at the Euro-Bioimaging Nodes are:

- Available for users, students, and facility staff
- Taught in English
- Open for anyone to apply to

In 2023,
259
training
courses
were open
to external
participants
at 30 Nodes

Below: The Dutch CLEM Node organised the 25th anniversary edition of the Utrecht EM workshops with 24 participants from 11 countries.

OUR NODES IN 2023

Above: This photo is from one of the hands-on sessions of the annual Quantitative Fluorescence Microscopy Course organised by PPBI. In this specific session students saw multidimensional imaging in a widefield system combining multichannel, z-stack and tiles.

“ 2023 was a positive year for our Node, with some achievements in technological development, recruitment of personnel in several facilities, providing a scientific support to a high number of users.

MMMI Italian Node coordinating team

Right: The Portuguese Brain Imaging Network is at the forefront in the neurosciences field, providing access to different types of advanced technologies for neuroimaging, including functional EEG in correlation with MRI.

Above, top: Functional imaging during the annual PhD course of the Erasmus Optical Imaging Centre (OIC). Photo courtesy of ERASMUS MC OIC Node.

Above, bottom: Istvan Balint Szücs, using the High Content Screening (HCS) Spinning Disk confocal microscope at the Center for Advanced Bioimaging (CAB), University of Copenhagen, to investigate spontaneous miscarriage. Photo courtesy of Danish BioImaging.

Above: In this photo, a user project is underway at the Dutch High-Throughput Node, University of Leiden. Automated imaging of multiple plates for live phenotypic screening is being set-up with the HTM operator of the Dutch High-Throughput Node Dr. Kostas Tassis (University Leiden).

Left: The PETtrace 800 cyclotron went through a Ten Years Life Extension and Refurbishment upgrade program at the Medical & Preclinical Imaging Hungary Node.

Above: A Quantitative Phase imaging system (QPI) is measuring living cells and their dynamics at the new location of the Biophotonics Core Facility at Brno University of Technology, part of the Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Node Brno.

“ *At DIMP NEUROMED, lots of external users were attracted by the imaging facility, with an evident net increase. We acquired new computing systems to store and analyse all data! It is particularly clear that the main demand is also on new data analytics, besides the traditional imaging service.*

Prof. Dr. Nicola D'Ascenzo
DIMP NEUROMED

“ *2023 was exceptionally good in terms of publications, companies as users, and receiving grant money.*

Marc van Zandoort
Facility for Multimodal Imaging
AMMI Maastricht

Right, top: Rumen Stamatov, from the Sofia BioImaging Node, Bulgaria, visualises cellular imaging data in 3D.

Right, bottom: Hans Blom, Swedish NMI, MINFLUX PSF alignment.

“

2023 was a good year since after years of effort of LCAM members in the NL-Biolmaging board, the Netherlands roadmap proposal was granted which will result in major equipment investments in the near future.

Mark Hink, Van Leeuwenhoek Center for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM)
Functional Imaging Flagship Node Amsterdam

Above: The CAPI Node, hosted at Charles University in Prague, is fully equipped with state of the art multi-modality preclinical imaging instrumentation for in vivo testing of novel drugs and diagnostic tools. The equipment includes a 7T MRI scanner for small animal imaging.

Every year, IMCF BIOCEV, part of our Prague Node, runs an imaging contest to award their users with the best images. Here, Node staff and winners from 2023.

A demonstration of microscopy techniques was held at the “Researchers’ Night” to the public at University of Debrecen, part of our Cellular Imaging Hungary Node. (picture taken at the University of Debrecen).

The team at BC LEM core facility in České Budějovice, part of the Prague Node, loading a grid into a cryoholder prior to cryo-TEM observation.

AUSTRIA

Austrian BioImaging/CMI

Node contact: Baubak Bajoghli

Website: austrian-bioimaging.at

FACILITIES

 22

EXTERNAL USERS

 >50

USER PUBLICATIONS

 n/a

REMOTE USERS

 <10

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

 2

STAFF INVOLVED

 >40

- The Node received funding for the collaborative ISIDORE JRA project VIRAL.
- Baubak Bajoghli received Science 2023 award by PHOENIX Group.
- Node staff hosted Euro-BioImaging Hub team visit in March 2023.
- The Node produced its first Annual Report, covering 2022-2023. Read it here:

https://austrian-bioimaging.at/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/CMI_AnnualReport-22-23.pdf

BULGARIA

Sofia BioImaging Node

Node contact: Stoyno Stoynov

Website: dnarepair.bas.bg/eurobioimaging.bg/site/

FACILITIES

 1

EXTERNAL USERS

 9

USER PUBLICATIONS

 n/a

REMOTE USERS

 n/a

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

 1

STAFF INVOLVED

 9

- Node received 1 970 000 Euro grant from the Bulgarian National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures.
- New machines include: BD FACSDiscover™ S8 Cell Sorter with BD CellView™ Image Technology and BD SpectralFX™ Technology.

CZECHIA

Advanced Light and Electron Microscopy Node Prague

Node contact: Aleš Benda

Website: czech-bioimaging.cz/euro-bi/

FACILITIES

6

EXTERNAL USERS

349

USER PUBLICATIONS

94

REMOTE USERS

14

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

17

STAFF INVOLVED

34.1

- The Node was awarded nearly 10 Mil EUR to upgrade its equipment in 2024-2026 (infrastructure investment funding for the project “Modernisation of the VVI Czech-Biolmaging”). Funding from LM 2023050 Czech-Biolmaging (1.5 M Euros a year) covers operating costs.
- IMCF at BIOCEV acquired high-end imaging platform Nikon iLas2 Ring-TIRF with photostimulation - a new wide-field microscope with Ring-TIRF illumination and photoactivation/FRAP module.
- The Node has actively engaged in European projects providing user access as part of ISIDORE.

CZECHIA

Advanced Light Microscopy and Medical Imaging Node Brno

Node contact: Michal Mikl

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-and-medical-imaging-Node-brno-cz

FACILITIES

4

EXTERNAL USERS

69

USER PUBLICATIONS

47

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

14

STAFF INVOLVED

26.7

- The Node benefits from funding from National Infrastructure for Biological and Medical imaging CZ grants.
- New instruments include a Zeiss LSM 980 at the Biophotonics core facility.
- Human MRI facility started the development of novel data processing tools for multi-echo fMRI data.
- Technological developments at the Node include new chambers for holographic microscopy, new MR-data processing tools, new methods for quantification of T1 in myocardium and new QUEST and AI-based methods for MRS quantification.

CZECHIA

Center for Advanced Preclinical Imaging (CAPI)

Node contact: Ludek Sefc

Website: capi.lf1.cuni.cz/en/address-capi

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

28

USER PUBLICATIONS

11

REMOTE USERS

16

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

4

STAFF INVOLVED

10

- The Node acquired a Kaer Labs Open Optical Imaging System for Fluorescence-guided Surgery.
- Together with TU Dresden described novel approaches in regulating tumor metabolism.
- The Node is developing ThyroPIX: a new generation camera for thyroid glands and small organs imaging by nuclear medicine methods.
- The Node hosted a student supported via Fulbright stipend.

DENMARK

Danish BioImaging Infrastructure

Node contact: Clara Prats, Sonia Garcia

Website: dbi-infra.eu

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

254

USER PUBLICATIONS

92

REMOTE USERS

15

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

10

STAFF INVOLVED

5

- DaMBIC (SDU) received new Nikon AX multiphoton microscope. The Core Facility for Advanced BioImaging (UCPH) got an analytical Electron microscope S/TEM (FEI) + EDS. The CFIM (UCPH) facility has purchased a Carl Zeiss Elyra 7 to perform SIM and dual colour SMLM.
- The DaMBIC infrastructure supported over 40 grant applications in different fields in 2023.
- The new DBI infrastructure team relocated to a bigger office space.
- DBI-INFRA Image Analysis Core Facility (IACF) officially started its open-access image analysis services on September 1st, 2023.
- Node produced its first Annual Report, covering 2022-2023. Read it here:

https://www.danishbioimaging.dk/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/DBI-INFRA_Report2022-23.pdf

EMBL

Euro-BioImaging EMBL Node

Node contact: Virginia Pierini

Website: eurobioimaging-access.eu/Nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-facility-embl

FACILITIES

4

EXTERNAL USERS

178

USER PUBLICATIONS

76

REMOTE USERS

54

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

8

STAFF INVOLVED

19.5

- The Node is working on developments for the following technologies: Brillouin microscopy, Oblique plane microscopy, EasyGrid, Serial 'lift-out' for in situ structural biology, Dynamic MINFLUX imaging, Cryo-FIB lift-out for in situ structural biology (together with the Mahamid group and Zeiss, Leica and Oxford Instruments), an automated trimming tool for the ultramicrotome (together with Leica), Cell 3D Positioning by Optical encoding (C3PO).

- EMBL Imaging Centre 2023 highlights are available here:

<https://embl.org/about/info/imaging-centre/blog/2024/02/embl-ic-highlights-of-2023/>

FINLAND

Finnish Advanced Microscopy Node (FiAM)

Node contact: Irina Belaia

Website: eurobioimaging.fi/FIAM/

FACILITIES

8

EXTERNAL USERS

135

USER PUBLICATIONS

181

REMOTE USERS

35

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

15

STAFF INVOLVED

26

- FiAM received 7.22 Mil EUR of investments from the Research Council of Finland FIRI 2023 funding to upgrade instruments and services.
- FiAM is beta-testing the Aurox clarity for live cell imaging, establishing analysis tools for hyperspectral SRS imaging data, developing on custom-built optical tweezers set-up.
- FiAM is developing optimized sample preparation protocols for volumeEM technologies and establishing workflow for volumeEM data sharing and reuse.
- FiAM developed Ocul-AR, a mobile app to guide researchers and students in becoming independent microscopy users with the help of augmented reality.

FINLAND

Finnish Biomedical Imaging Node (FiBI)

Node contact: Tiina Saanijoki

Website: eurobioimaging.fi/FiBI/

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

170

USER PUBLICATIONS

276

REMOTE USERS

19

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

10

STAFF INVOLVED

93

- Turku PET Centre acquired a new Raycan small animal PET/CT.
- FiBI contributes to development of a multichannel optically pumped magnetometer (OPM) system in collaboration with Aalto University and MEGIN Ltd.
- Development of artificial intelligence-based tools for dementia diagnostics in EU2020 Horizon project AI-Mind, proposing novel biomarkers based on functional brain imaging.
- Developing stimulus and monitoring devices for MEG and MRI/fMRI as well as contributing to the MEG vendor's R&D validation projects.
- Development of zero echo fMRI as a tool across most preclinical imaging manufactures as well as testing its clinical suitability.

FRANCE

France BioImaging Node (FBI)

Node contact: Caroline Thiriet

Website: france-bioimaging.org/

FACILITIES

25

EXTERNAL USERS

876

USER PUBLICATIONS

246

REMOTE USERS

18

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

66

STAFF INVOLVED

209

- FBI launched 2 calls of the “Africa-France Joint Initiative for Biological Imaging”, pairing imaging scientists and researchers in Africa and France.
- FBI organised a FBI.data Sprint week to work on FAIR image data management.
- Technology development areas include: Correlative X-ray and Electron Microscopy (CXEM), LM/AFM correlative microscopy, Lattice lightsheet - ideal for high-resolution imaging of live samples, and sequential smFISH for high-resolution spatial transcriptomics.
- Toulouse & Alsace Nodes joined France-BioImaging, becoming part of the Euro-BioImaging Node in 2024.

HUNGARY

Cellular Imaging Hungary

Node contact: János Szöllősi, György Vamosi
Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/cellular-imaging-hungary

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

101

USER PUBLICATIONS

~100

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

5

STAFF INVOLVED

9

- A Beckman Coulter CytoFLEX cell sorter with 4 lasers was acquired at the University of Debrecen.
- The sub-Node in Szeged participated in a project funded by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative; Semmelweis University (Budapest) in Marie Curie Training Networks; the University of Debrecen in a JPND project for the investigation of Parkinson's disease.
- A demonstration of microscopy techniques was held at the "Researchers' Night" for the public.
- 33 PhD defenses took place based on research utilising the Node's facilities.
- An ISIDORE project was awarded to Dr. Veronika Huntošová (University of Kosice, Slovakia) for studying hypericin-nanoparticle uptake for photodynamic therapy at the University of Debrecen (Pevná et al, JPPB B: Photobiology).

HUNGARY

Medical and Preclinical Imaging Hungary

Node contact: Viktória Zsófia Arató
Website: <https://eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/medical-and-preclinical-imaging-hungary>

FACILITIES

4

EXTERNAL USERS

22

USER PUBLICATIONS

70

REMOTE USERS

4

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

2

STAFF INVOLVED

19.4

- The PETtrace 800 cyclotron went through a Ten Years Life Extension and Refurbishment upgrade program.
- Ongoing projects with international and national companies of radiolabelling of new type pharmaceutical ingredients (in pre-clinical and clinical phase).
- Several grants and scholarships were awarded to staff members of the Node by their university and the Technology Transfer Center.
- In 2023, 3 students successfully completed their PhD program with support of the Node.

ISRAEL

Israel BioImaging

Node contact: Michal Neeman

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/israel-bioimaging

FACILITIES

7

EXTERNAL USERS

50

USER PUBLICATIONS

60

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

5

STAFF INVOLVED

20

- A new spinning disk confocal, the Olympus ixplore spin, arrived at the Technion sub-Node.
- Users are funded predominantly by the Israel Science Foundation and ERC.
- Thirty industry users undertook projects at the Israel BioImaging Node.
- University of Haifa sub-Node contributed to ANERIS project training course on AI tools for image restoration.

ITALY

Advanced Light Microscopy Italian Node

Node contact: Dr. Seetharaman Parashuraman

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/advanced-light-microscopy-italian-Node/

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

72

USER PUBLICATIONS

23

REMOTE USERS

7

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

3

STAFF INVOLVED

15.5

- New instruments include: Confocal super-resolution STED microscope Leica Stellaris SP8 + FLIM in Padua.
- Technology developments include novel probes for EM, technology for identifying CTCs; Vibrationally-resonant/third-order sum frequency generation microscope; Combination of optical tweezers with single molecule fluorescence microscopy; Dual color 3D super-resolution microscopy; Combination of Expansion Microscopy with Super-resolution PALM; Inverted LSM for automated large sections reconstruction.
- The Node benefits from funding from a number of projects and was active in PhD programmes.

ITALY

Digital Imaging Multimodal Platform Neuromed - DIMP NEUROMED

Node contact: Prof. Nicola D'Ascenzo

Website: neuromed.it

FACILITIES

8

EXTERNAL USERS

12

USER PUBLICATIONS

12

REMOTE USERS

1

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

0

STAFF INVOLVED

4

- >10 Mil EUR funding obtained from Italian National Recovery Plan involving the use of the Node's imaging facility.
- The Node participated in Horizon 2020 project PETAL (PET in Agriculture and Life).
- The Node worked on the development of portable Positron Emission Tomography systems including a helmet PET system for dedicated brain imaging, and a portable plant PET system (see INNOVATION section).

ITALY

MMMI - Multimodal Molecular Imaging Italian Node

Node contact: Enzo Terreno

Website: www.mmmi.unito.it/

FACILITIES

9

EXTERNAL USERS

25

USER PUBLICATIONS

10

REMOTE USERS

56

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

1

STAFF INVOLVED

35.5

- Node acquired new NIRF/BLI modules interfacing to the existing PET/SPECT/CT scanner and a new PET/MRI scanner.
- Technology developments include: Connectomic analysis of regional brain metabolism; MRI preclinical Imaging protocols and analysis on liver steatosis/fibrosis, MRI preclinical imaging Resting-State protocols for connectivity & structural brain analysis, development of preclinical MRI sequences for tumor pH imaging.
- Further developments of clinical MRI dedicated sequences, for the evaluation of bone densitometry.
- Node staff participate in Lessons to Neuroscience PhD programme and the MORPHOPHEN Erasmus Mundi Master's programme.

ITALY

Phase Contrast Imaging Flagship Node Trieste

Node contact: Giuliana Tromba

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/phase-contrast-imaging-flagship-Node-trieste

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

15

USER PUBLICATIONS

24

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

2

STAFF INVOLVED

2

- The Node acquired a new phantom to perform studies on human-like lungs kept inflated by an adequate pumping system.
- The Node is a partner in the recently funded: 'GAP' - image-guided computational and experimental Analysis of fractured Patients - European training network <https://gapmscaproject.com/>
- Node received funding for the collaborative ISIDORE JRA project VIRAL.

NETHERLANDS

Correlative Light Microscopy Dutch Flagship Node

Node contact: Judith Klumperman, Nalan Liv

Website: microscopie.nl

FACILITIES

3

EXTERNAL USERS

27

USER PUBLICATIONS

~60

REMOTE USERS

5

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

4

STAFF INVOLVED

8

- The Node was awarded a number of important grants from NWO and Dutch National Growth Fund.
- New instruments include Xenium In Situ (UMCG) and a new self-built correlative fluorescence and ion beam SEM.
- NL Minister of Education, Culture and Science was highly interested in Dutch Microscopy in 2023 and visited the awardees of roadmaps, including NL-Biolmaging, and attended the opening of the new EM building in Utrecht.
- The Node organised the 25th year of Utrecht EM workshops

<https://cellmicroscopy.nl/workshops/>

NETHERLANDS

Dutch High Field Imaging Hub

Node contact: Dennis Klomp
Website: highfieldmri.nl

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

52

USER PUBLICATIONS

~100

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

4

STAFF INVOLVED

10

- New instruments include a test console to prepare for 14T MRI and a Gradient booster for 1.5T, 3T and 7T MRI.
- Grants awarded to the Node include IHI Illuminate, Eurostars femscan and selfscan, NWO maestro and NWO holistic.
- The Node is working to develop 14T MRI: the world's strongest whole body MRI system, planned to be operational at Radboud Nijmegen in 2026, funded by NWO.

NETHERLANDS

Erasmus MC OIC - Advanced Light Microscopy Rotterdam Node

Node contact: Gert-Jan Kremers
Website: erasmusoic.nl

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

4

USER PUBLICATIONS

31

REMOTE USERS

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

4

STAFF INVOLVED

8

- The Node upgraded an RCM confocal into an AI-driven smart microscope for image guided functional imaging.
- The OIC is the lead core facility in the Convergence Flagship consortium CIFIC, to promote collaboration between Erasmus MC and TU Delft.
- The OIC image analysis course is now part of the Erasmus MC Graduation school.

NETHERLANDS

Facility of Multimodal Imaging - AMMI Maastricht

Node contact: Marc A.M.J. van Zandvoort

Website: www.eurobioimaging-access.eu/nodes/facility-of-excellence-in-imaging---alm-and-molecular-imaging-node-maastricht

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

~50

USER PUBLICATIONS

n/a

REMOTE USERS

n/a

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

4

STAFF INVOLVED

16

- The Optical imaging part of the Node obtained a national grant of 2.5 Mil EUR.
- The Node acquired a new Multiphoton intravital and stimulated Raman spectroscopy and a multiphoton endoscope.
- All Node staff is involved in the Bachelor Biomedical sciences (BBS) program, the Master of Science (MBS) and others.
- The Node participates in EU projects - PETAL, MSCA-ITN THERADNET, EuCanImage, IMPRESS, UNLOCC.

NETHERLANDS

High Throughput Microscopy Dutch Flagship Node

Node contact: Sylvia Le Dévédec

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/nodes/high-throughput-microscopy-dutch-flagship-node

FACILITIES

2

EXTERNAL USERS

20

USER PUBLICATIONS

10

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

0

STAFF INVOLVED

4

- The Node purchased different compound libraries including the GPCR targeting compound library, updated FDA library, NRF2 pathway activating library.
- The Node purchased an automated screening system with ImageXpress and dedicated robotics.
- Busy year in terms of outreach including meeting with minister Robert Dijkgraaf in Leiden and developing a Lego microscope workshop for kids at Leiden Science family day.
- The Node organized many training courses for PhD/PD students on BioImaging and FAIR image data.

NETHERLANDS

Preclinical Imaging Centre (PRIME) - Molecular Imaging Dutch Node

Node contact: Amanda Kiliaan, Wilma Janssen

Website: radboudumc.nl/en/research/radboud-technology-centers/imaging/preclinical-imaging-center

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

7

USER PUBLICATIONS

n/a

REMOTE USERS

n/a

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

6

STAFF INVOLVED

7

- Through the NL-BioImaging Roadmap the Node receives more than 1 Mil EUR for installing a next-generation 3- and 4-photon intravital microscopy platform in PRIME.
- Award of the NWO Perspectief grant for upgrading the SPECT/CT scanner and a new high-end CT system.
- Using funds from the NWO-Zwaartekracht funding IMAGINE!, a new laser type for low-repetition high-pulse-energy 3- and 4-photon excitation and ultra-deep tissue microscopy was installed.

NETHERLANDS

Population Imaging Flagship Node Rotterdam

Node contact: Ilva Vanhouwelingen

Website: populationimaging.eu

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

107

USER PUBLICATIONS

7

REMOTE USERS

n/a

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

3

STAFF INVOLVED

2.5

- The Node undertook major advances in its management as the Erasmus MC Imaging Office - the gateway to the combined knowledge and skills of the Radiology & Nuclear Medicine department of the Erasmus MC - is being established, and will integrate with the Population Imaging Flagship Node.
- The Node participates in EuCanImage, canServ, EOSC4Cancer & EUCAIM EU projects.
- The Node contributed to EUCAIM platform's public catalogue of cancer imaging datasets from the repositories of the AI4HI cancer imaging projects.
- The Node developed multiple tools for use with XNAT, and is working on an image viewer with possibilities for tailored additional functionality.

NETHERLANDS

The van Leeuwenhoek Centre for Advanced Microscopy (LCAM)

Node contact: Mark Hink

Website: lcam.nl

FACILITIES

3

EXTERNAL USERS

8

USER PUBLICATIONS

~40

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

6

STAFF INVOLVED

11

- The Node acquired a Leica Stellaris 8 confocal.
- The Node was part of the successful NL-BioImaging roadmap application.
- Multiple LCAM staff members were involved in the main organisation of the ELMI 2023 meeting.
- The Node worked to develop FLIM-STED.

NETHERLANDS

Wageningen Imaging and Spectroscopy Hub (WISH) - ALM and Molecular Imaging Node

Node contact: Johannes Hohlbein

Website: [eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/wageningen-imaging-and-spectroscopy-hub-\(wish\)---alm-and-molecular-imaging-Node-wageningen](http://eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/wageningen-imaging-and-spectroscopy-hub-(wish)---alm-and-molecular-imaging-Node-wageningen)

FACILITIES

2

EXTERNAL USERS

19

USER PUBLICATIONS

~40

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

7

STAFF INVOLVED

3.1

- The Node received Funding for 3D functional imaging confocal (NL-Bioimaging Roadmap).
- The Node contributed to TARDIS (single particle tracking algorithm) published in Nature Methods.
- The Node's annual PhD and Postdoc course for the research schools VLAG and EPS was very highly appreciated and scored by all 24 participants.
- The Node was very active in training, providing 127 personal training sessions.

NORWAY

NorMIC Oslo - Advanced Light Microscopy Node Oslo

Node contact: Oddmund Bakke

Website: mn.uio.no/ibv/english/research/infrastructure/facilities/life-science/imaging/normic

FACILITIES

1

EXTERNAL USERS

56

USER PUBLICATIONS

27

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

3

STAFF INVOLVED

5

- The Node acquired a Zeiss LSM 980 Airyscan.
- The Node and the Oslo network was awarded 0.6 Mil EUR including a position to support the network for the next 3 years.
- The Node organized workshops on Biological Microscopy and on imaging processing.
- The Node co-organized a successful Nordic BNMI symposium in Odense, Denmark.
- Preparation is underway for the move of half of the NorMIC Oslo Node into the University of Oslo Life Science Building, joining it with the facility at the University Hospital creating a larger combined NorMIC Oslo Node.

NORWAY

NORMOLIM, Norwegian Molecular Imaging Infrastructure

Node contact: Lili Zhang, Jin Li

Website: normolim.w.uib.no

FACILITIES

3

EXTERNAL USERS

28

USER PUBLICATIONS

9

REMOTE USERS

2

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

1

STAFF INVOLVED

7.5

- The Node is working on the PseudoPET with Luxembourg. The project aims to use multimodal MRI and AI to generate PET images of hypoxia. In this project, immunodeficient rats are implanted with human glioblastoma specimens, and FLT PET as well as multimodal MRI are performed. All animal work is performed at Dept of Biomedicine and MIC, and image analysis is done at Luxembourg Institute of Health
- Developments at the Node include gluCEST and cardiac MRE.

POLAND

Advanced Light Microscopy Node Poland

Node contact: Jędrzej Szymański

Website: amf.nencki.edu.pl

FACILITIES

4

EXTERNAL USERS

33

USER PUBLICATIONS

25

REMOTE USERS

0

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

0

STAFF INVOLVED

7

- The Node acquired a super-resolution microscope - the Nanoimager from ONI.
- The Node got support from the Ministry of Science and Higher Education to maintain the technologies in their portfolio.
- The Node also received funding to support user access via the National User Access grant scheme.
- The Node hosted several visits of young researchers and school pupils interested in life sciences, allowing them to familiarize themselves with state of the art imaging techniques.

PORTUGAL

Brain Imaging Network (BIN)

Node contact: Miguel Castelo-Branco

Website: uc.pt/en/brainimaging/

FACILITIES

13

EXTERNAL USERS

8

USER PUBLICATIONS

28

REMOTE USERS

3

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

3

STAFF INVOLVED

7

- The Node benefits from many funding schemes and all scanners have been upgraded.
- The Node is involved in projects to study potential impacts of prenatal diet on neurodevelopmental diseases; innovative treatment for neuropsychiatric disorders using neurofeedback and Neurostimulation.
- The Node is participating in major EU projects - STIPED combining NeuroImaging and Neurostimulation and AIMS-2-Trials combining MR and PET to study biomarkers in Autism.
- The Node is very active in communication and outreach, participating in a number of science communication events, organises courses and had regular presence in the main national media (magazines and several TV shows).

PORTUGAL

Portuguese Platform of BioImaging (PPBI)

Node contact: Luisa Cortes

Website: ppbi.pt

FACILITIES

 15

EXTERNAL USERS

 125

USER PUBLICATIONS

 232

REMOTE USERS

 15

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

 24

STAFF INVOLVED

 38

- The Node acquired many new instruments such as: High-content screening systems, a multiplexing system, microscopes for cellular observations, a Scanning Electron Microscope; a combined Atomic force and fluorescence microscope, a biodynamic system for 3D-mechanical stimulation, super-resolution SIM systems and a large sample light-sheet system.
- The Node organised FOM2023 and NEUBIAS conferences.
- The Node was active in job shadowing with Global BioImaging and CTLS, hosting facility staff from Mexico and Spain respectively.
- Several public engagement initiatives such as the celebration of the “International day of light” were organised by the Node.

SLOVENIA

SiMBION

Node contact: Primož Pelicon

Website: symbion.mf.uni-lj.si/en/home-2/

FACILITIES

 16

EXTERNAL USERS

 24

USER PUBLICATIONS

 15

REMOTE USERS

 1

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

 0

STAFF INVOLVED

 4

- The Node acquired a new TOF mass spectrometer for advanced ICP-MS imaging (National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana) to probe micron sized trace element features in solid samples and determine the elemental composition of individual nanoparticles.
- The Node participated in the Horizon Europe EU project ReMade@ARI (<https://remade-project.eu/>) to explore the properties and structures of recyclable materials.
- University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical faculty participates in the project FunContrAPest: “Novel Fungal Proteins as Biopesticides for Control of Challenging Invasive Alien Agricultural Pests.”
- The Node published micro-PIXE developments, see INNOVATION, p. 33.

SWEDEN

Swedish National Microscopy Infrastructure

Node contact: Hjalmar Brismar, Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez

Website: nmisweden.se

FACILITIES

5

EXTERNAL USERS

120

USER PUBLICATIONS

95

REMOTE USERS

25

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

25

STAFF INVOLVED

30

- The Swedish Research Council (VR) has agreed to continue to support NMI until 2028.
- The Node acquired many new instruments, including lightsheet and super-resolutions systems for SIM, SMLM, and MINFLUX; EM systems for Array Tomography and improved systems for FIB-SEM and cryo-lamella preparation.
- The Node is involved in technology development in smart microscopy, volume EM, Clearing and Expansion microscopy, tissue engineering.
- The image analysis sub-Node is developing new workflows for cell segmentation and classification using QuPath, Ilastik, and Python.

UNITED KINGDOM

The UK Node

Node contact: Georgina Fletcher

Website: eurobioimaging.eu/Nodes/uk-Node

FACILITIES

14

EXTERNAL USERS

202

USER PUBLICATIONS

134

REMOTE USERS

9

TRAINING COURSES ORGANIZED

5

STAFF INVOLVED

47.6

- The Node acquired many new instruments, including super-resolution systems from SMLM, SPT, SRRFnTIRF, new MassSpec imaging system TOF-ICP-MS, Functional and live imaging systems for FLIM, a Magnetic Particle Imaging scanner, lightsheet system, a FIB-SEM system as part of a correlative imaging pipeline, and Imaging Cell Sorter.
- King's College London hosted a grand opening of the LMF following a 6 month ~£1M refurbishment with several talks and commercial engagement.
- At ESRIC, the Node was involved in the first Apprentices programme for 17 year olds. Apprentices were working in the Advanced Imaging Facility with super-resolution equipment. The apprentices have gone forwards to either university or to apprenticeships with microscopy manufacturers.

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Front cover image, top: Image by Alasdair Edgar, King's College, London. "Adult Mouse Head Sagittal Section".

Front cover image, bottom: Image by Arina Rybina, EMBL. "Captivating nuclei mountains space". Artistic visualisation of cell nuclei imaged with a confocal fluorescence microscope. (3D surface plot, magenta: DNA, turquoise: Nuclear pore complexes, the peaks height are reflecting fluorescence intensity profiles).

Back cover image: Imaged by Nikky Corthout, VIB Imaging Core Leuven / Sample provided by Franck Maurinot, Pierre Vanderhaeghen lab, VIB Center for Brain and Disease Research. "Human cortical organoid". High resolution confocal tilescan, z-stack.

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